

Fostering Collective Intelligence in CKAN Open Data Portals: Dataset Revisioning and Feedback Mechanisms

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Abstract. The concept of the "wisdom of crowds" illustrates an emergent property where groups of individuals can be smarter than the smartest members within those groups. This idea is fundamental to collective intelligence, and modern platforms such as GitHub, Wikidata, and OpenStreetMap exemplify this principle. This study investigates how open data ecosystems, particularly Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) - based portals, can adopt similar mechanisms to foster community engagement and enhance system functionality. Upon investigating various open data portals, we found that there were minimal ways for users to contribute back to the system regarding existing resources. Some portals did provide limited ways to contribute, such as feedback forms, but these were not intuitive enough to facilitate direct collaboration. To address this, we propose integrating resource revisioning and issue-tracking mechanisms inspired by GitHub to allow users to improve datasets collaboratively. This study outlines the technical implementation of these features, including schema changes such as creating new database tables to handle dataset revisions and their logs, issue tracking, comment histories, issue statuses for specific data resources, and publisher decisions on user-submitted revisions. Moreover, comprehensive user interface (UI) updates were also introduced, featuring new tabs and dedicated pages for managing dataset revisions and issue tracking. These enhancements not only increase user engagement by providing intuitive collaboration tools but also support future scalability through modular extensions for CKAN portals. This modular approach ensures seamless integration with existing CKAN-based systems, facilitating widespread adoption across open data portals. By integrating these proposed changes, we aim to encourage the open data community to become more active, collectively improve the system, and establish a more circular and sustainable ecosystem.

Keywords: CKAN, Open Data Portals, Open Data Ecosystems, Collective Intelligence, Crowdsourcing, Circularity, Dataset Revisioning, Feedback Mechanisms, FAIR Data Principles.

1 Introduction

Open data has become a cornerstone of modern digital governance, enabling transparency, innovation, and evidence-based decision-making across sectors [23] [3]. Governments, organizations, and research institutions worldwide rely on open data portals to disseminate information and promote data reuse [34]. Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN), a widely adopted open source platform, is the most common software these open data portals are based on [2]. It provides a robust resource management system for publishing, cataloging, and accessing data resources. However, despite their wide adaptability and potential, CKAN-based portals often face challenges in ensuring data quality, usability, and user collaboration [30].

Realizing the full potential of open data relies more than just on accessibility. The quality of the data, its relevance to user needs, and its adaptability to diverse cases also serve as critical factors [26]. The majority of datasets are in their raw form and might not be catered to what the users need. In that case, more technical users download the datasets, clean them, and transform them for their own use cases. However, multiple users might be processing the same data for similar use cases but have no way to share their refined versions with each other or the users that access that dataset. Currently, there is no mechanism that allows users to contribute their enhanced dataset versions back into the portal [11]. Although technical users might be able to process the data themselves, non-technical users are more likely to communicate with data publishers or other expert users to express their data needs or even suggest improvements to the datasets. It also requires a mechanism that enables prompt communication and collaboration between data publishers and users, as well as among users themselves, fostering a community-driven environment based on the principles of collective intelligence.

Collective intelligence leverages the community's contributions to solve complex problems collaboratively in small steps [24]. GitHub, Wikidata, and OpenStreetMap have successfully implemented the core principles of collective intelligence to build a community and address the aforementioned problems. While they have tackled these problems within their ecosystems, they still remain a challenge in the open data community. Drawing inspiration from these initiatives, particularly GitHub, we propose to address them through CKAN extensions: Data Revision and Issue Management.

The dataset revisioning extension allows all users to modify the data resources in the portal and commit them back into the system. Each revision is hierarchically linked with the original resource, preserving the original resource while allowing users access to enhanced ones. To maintain the data quality within the portal, each revision is subject to approval by the publisher. It is accepted if the publisher does not approve or reject it within 30 days of uploading. On the other hand, the issue management system, also inspired by GitHub, provides a structured way for users to report errors, express data needs, suggest improvements, or request more information about datasets. It allows users to engage with all publishers, stakeholders, and users directly.

Through the integration of these extensions as CKAN plugins, we aim to create a more circular and user-driven open data ecosystem. They would also align open data portals with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), improving the findability, usability, and reusability of datasets. In the subsequent sections, we explore related works, establish the background for the study, propose design and evaluation strategies for these extensions.

2 Related Work

The growing popularity of open data has led to an increasing focus on tools and platforms that facilitate data sharing and reuse. CKAN, as an open-source data management system, has been widely adopted by governments, academic institutions, and organizations[2]. Studies highlight its effectiveness in enabling data publication and access, yet they also identify gaps in user engagement and collaborative features. These limitations have prompted research into extending CKAN's capabilities to support more interactive and community-centric functionalities.

Recent research on collaborative platforms such as GitHub and OpenStreetMap underscores the value of community-driven content improvement [8, 1]. GitHub's issue-tracking system, for instance, allows users to report bugs, suggest enhancements, and engage in discussions with developers. Similarly, OpenStreetMap relies on user contributions to continuously update and refine geographic data. These models demonstrate how collective intelligence can enhance data quality and usability through user participation[13, 10, 20, 12, 41, 43]. Their success illustrates the potential of embedding community workflows into data infrastructures, a concept still lacking in the open data portal ecosystem.

Additionally, crowd-sourced systems have been proven to enable circularity, empowering end users to contribute back to the system, which, in turn, improves the underlying infrastructure[42, 6]. However, the application of collective intelligence in open data portals remains underexplored. Although some portals incorporate basic feedback mechanisms, they often lack the sophistication and user-friendly interfaces found on platforms like GitHub[15]. Moreover, none of the explored portals provide users with the ability to upload improved versions of datasets, limiting the potential for collaborative refinement.

Complementary to these collaborative models, recent work explores version control frameworks for datasets that mirror software development practices. For instance, semantic versioning systems such as "major.minor.patch" are being proposed to enhance dataset traceability and ensure FAIR compliance [17]. Platforms like DataHub and tools like DVC and lakeFS enable Git-like operations—branching, merging, and history tracking—over structured data [7, 21, 39]. Such mechanisms address technical challenges around reproducibility and reuse, but they remain disconnected from mainstream open data portals.

Our work extends these insights by designing and evaluating a framework that integrates dataset revisioning and feedback mechanisms in CKAN-based portals. Unlike prior work, which primarily focuses on basic feedback mecha-

nisms, our approach seeks to incorporate structured versioning and user-driven improvements to datasets, bridging the gap between open data repositories and collaborative data curation. This approach aligns with the principles of open innovation, emphasizing collaboration and creating shared value in the open data domain.

3 Background

3.1 Collective Intelligence

Collective intelligence is often defined as a group of individuals performing a task collectively, reflecting collective decision capability that is at least as good as or better than any individual of the group [25, 9, 22]. Malone et al. explore the evolution of collective intelligence through the years and define modern collective intelligence through three key elements: “(1) groups of individuals (2) acting collectively (3) in ways that seem intelligent” [25]. GitHub, Wikidata, Wikipedia, and OpenStreetMap exemplify how these three key elements potentially lead to creating and maintaining high-quality resources collaboratively. The proposed extensions also hold the potential to follow these principles and transform open data portals into dynamic, community-driven platforms that foster collaboration and innovation.

3.2 Github

GitHub is a leading open-source software development platform that allows developers to store, share, and manage their code [12]. Founded in 2007, it has since grown to be adopted by major organizations like Spotify, Ford, P&G, and Arduino as a tool to manage their projects [16]. It provides developers with rich features like version control for managing changes, providing feedback about the code through creating issues, pulling requests for merging code, and tools for automating workflows [12]. Its collaborative environment allows open-source contributors and enterprise teams to collaborate globally, sharing innovations and building on each other’s progress [14]. Features like forks, branches, and GitHub Pages enable users to experiment with new ideas, contribute to existing projects, and deploy applications directly from their repositories. With millions of repositories and users worldwide, GitHub has become a cornerstone of the software development ecosystem [14, 12].

3.3 Wikidata

Wikidata is a crowdsourced knowledge graph built to complement other Wikimedia projects (e.g., Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons). It started in 2012 to centralize Wikipedia’s interlanguage links, with the idea to serve as a machine-readable open data repository with information that could then be fed to Wikipedia[33]. A diverse community of contributors populates it - both humans and machines - maintaining and updating the data and its relationships[29].

Wikidata has also seen uses beyond Wikimedia projects, serving as a knowledge base for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools and Information Retrieval (IR) systems like Scholia to manage scientific bibliographic data or as an ontological base for medical data[27, 40]. It also hosts relevant features with built-in support for multilingual collaboration[36].

A Collective Intelligence approach where the goal is to produce a more accurate result with collaboration than that made by a single system has seen promising results on Wikidata[37], with the first studies being made in its contributors' types and relations[32].

3.4 OpenStreetMap

OpenStreetMap is a free and open collaborative geographical database of the entire world to create an accurate, detailed, and localized representation of our world.

OpenStreetMap exemplifies collective intelligence by harnessing a diverse global community's localized expertise and continuous input to build and refine its mapping data, with decentralized contributions from individual users allowing for rapid updates and nuanced corrections that traditional mapping systems may overlook[18].

3.5 Open Data Portals

Open data portals are essential platforms for storing data as open resources, fostering transparency, and enabling innovation across various domains. They allow all public/private publishers to upload their data as open resources, which can then be accessed and reused by all users for various reasons, including research, innovation, policy making, and analysis. Although open data portals provide all the tools to open the data, one of their significant challenges is ensuring that the datasets are of high quality, well-documented, and easy to use. Other open-source initiatives such as GitHub, Wikidata, and OpenStreetMap (OSM) employ crowdsourcing to address this challenge. Similarly, collaborative input from users within these open data portals can play an impactful role in addressing these issues, enhancing both the usability and reliability of the data[31, 38, 4, 35, 28]. Fig 1 reflects one of the most used open data portals, harvesting data resources from all over Europe.

Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) CKAN is a widely used open-source resource management system designed to support the creation, management, sharing, and consumption of datasets. Its modular architecture makes it quite extensible. Most open data portals are based on top of CKAN architecture. It is adopted by various governments and organizations worldwide. Despite all its functions, it does not provide an intuitive way for users to collaborate and build a community around it. Although a few extensions existed on top of it to provide a feedback feature, it was limited to contact forms. It

Fig. 1. Screenshot of data.europa.eu, the European Data Portal.

turned out to be the basis of this study that introducing the features above could significantly enhance CKAN’s utility, transforming it from a data repository to a collaborative data curation platform.[5].

In the subsequent section of the methodology, we detail CKAN’s current state and propose changes to enhance its collective intelligence.

4 System Design and Implementation

In this section, we focus on describing the current state of CKAN, a globally used open data management system. Our goal is to explore and identify the areas to enhance collaboration and collective intelligence amongst its users. During this analysis, we identified two shortcomings from the perspective of collective intelligence. There was no possibility for users to be able to revise open data resources, nor did it provide any feedback mechanism to enable user participation, invalidating the very concept of inclusivity, circularity, and openness.

To address this, we proposed to implement these functionalities through CKAN extensions. Implementing them as extensions would allow all the current CKAN-based portals to be able to integrate these updates by just installing the extensions. We proposed database schema changes that would be required in the base schema to be able to incorporate these changes. Moreover, we also proposed the user interface changes required to allow users to access the revisioning and feedback system.

Our methodology ultimately aims to make CKAN more collaborative and user-centric by empowering communities to contribute actively to maintaining

and enhancing open data resources. These proposed changes can significantly improve the quality and reliability of datasets on CKAN-based portals, ultimately enhancing collective intelligence in the data portals and making them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

4.1 CKAN: Current State

In this section, we explore the functionality and limitations of CKAN, a widely used open data management system. As we explore below, it follows an orientation of the publisher-driven model, with limited opportunity for the users to contribute to the system. Figure 2 shows the landing page for the publisher after sign-in, which reflects the current state of the Organizations page in a base CKAN portal. It allows the data publishers to create an organization with associated contact information.

Fig. 2. The list of organizations, as seen from a publisher perspective

Fig. 3. The list of datasets for any publisher in a CKAN portal

A dataset consists of metadata and resources, which are the actual dataset files. From a list of datasets, if a publisher clicks on any selected dataset, it would be able to view all its metadata and resources associated with that dataset, as demonstrated in Figure 4).

Each resource of the dataset has its own associated metadata and a data file. As reflected in the Figure 5), it only allows users to download or preview the given resource. There is no option to be able to edit it, modify it or upload a processed version of it.

While the current state of CKAN follows a pretty standard format for a data management system, there is no mechanism for the user to provide any input into the system. However, we did find an extension that allowed the users to contact

Fig. 4. Details and resources of any given dataset in a CKAN portal

Fig. 5. Resources and their details in a CKAN portal

the publishers through a contact form or email. Nevertheless, we found it to be a non-interactive method. Some portals have a similar extension implemented. The United Kingdom Natural History Museum portal, based on CKAN, has a contact form integrated with its datasets (see Figure 6).

One of the advanced and well-maintained portals, Data.gouv.fr (the French data portal), does include a basic discussion section (see Figure 7). However, this portal is not based on CKAN technology.

Fig. 6. Contact form to provide feedback in the U.K. Natural History Museum open data portal

Fig. 7. The discussions section at a dataset on Data.gouv.fr, a trend-setter among data portals. Source: <https://www.data.gouv.fr>

4.2 Dataset Revisioning

For any ecosystem to be collaborative, it has not only to allow but also to make it easy for users to be a part of the ecosystem by contributing back to it. Similar is the case with current open data portals, which fail to provide mechanisms for users to contribute back into the system with corrective measures. In this study, we focus mostly on CKAN since most global open data portals are based

on CKAN. As discussed and demonstrated in the previous section, CKAN base currently does not have a feature that allows users to revise or update open datasets. Users are unable to push it back into the system once they make modifications in the datasets for their specific use cases or suggest general improvements in them. In the subsequent sections, we propose the schema changes and interface changes required for extending the CKAN base to integrate the resource revisioning mechanism.

Schema Changes The current CKAN database schema includes, among others, the tables *package* and *resource*. Our proposed extension would create a new table *revision*. This table will link to two resources: the original resource from which the revision started and the revision resource containing the user’s proposed changes. The table also includes information about the status — accepted or rejected— of the revision and the time that it was created and last modified. Figure 8 shows a detailed table diagram with the proposed fields and relations between the tables.

Fig. 8. Schema changes required to implement a revisioning system for dataset resources

UI/UX Changes The current user interface does not reflect any mechanisms for users to be able to do any operations on resources other than viewing it or downloading it, as observed in Figure 5. Users who view or download it usually process the data, clean it, analyze it, integrate it into their particular use case, and innovate with it. Still, they have no mechanism to share that transformed data or use case back into the system. We modified the existing user

interface and created new interfaces to address this. As reflected in Figure 9, we provided the option to revise any resource of the dataset in addition to previewing and downloading it. Whenever a user has a modified, cleaned, or transformed revision of any resource, they will click on the revision feature. Following it, the user will be directed towards the revision interface. The revision interface, as demonstrated in Figure 10, will allow the user to enter the details of the updated resource, such as name, description, and format. Also, it would allow uploading a new updated file associated with it.

Fig. 9. The interface for a user to initiate revision for any given resource

Fig. 10. The interface for entering resource revisioning details and uploading the updated file

Following the resource revision, it does not immediately show up in the portal. It first goes to the data publisher to be reviewed. If a publisher finds it a valuable addition to the essence of the dataset, they would approve it or otherwise reject it. It is reflected in Figure 11, the revision appears highlighted under the original resource for a publisher to view, accept, or reject. If it is rejected, the user is alerted, and the resource is archived for a month. If it is accepted, it starts appearing under the original resource and is accessible to all the users. It appears as a hierarchical sub-bullet under the original resource, see Figure 12. It is open to all users, and they can again view it, download it, and revise it.

Fig. 11. The interface for publisher to view/accept/reject the revision

Fig. 12. The interface showing how accepted revisions would view and be accessible to users

The crowd-based dataset revisioning mechanism aims to foster community engagement within the ecosystem. Currently, most open data ecosystems operate in a one-directional manner: datasets are published by companies and organizations, and users simply consume that data. There is limited opportunity for users to contribute back to the system. This proposed system would ensure circularity within the ecosystem, allowing data to flow in both directions and be improved collaboratively. It would encourage collaboration among publishers and users, as well as between users themselves, ultimately leading to a more innovative ecosystem.

4.3 Feedback Mechanisms

For any ecosystem to remain dynamic and user-centric, it must not only facilitate access to data but also encourage users to provide structured feedback. While dataset revisioning does provide a mechanism for users to contribute to the system, it does so only for users who are technical and able to process the resources to contribute. Other non-technical users who just access the data have no way of letting the publisher know of their feedback or suggestions regarding resources. Most existing open data portals, including CKAN-based systems, lack intuitive feedback mechanisms that empower users to engage with publishers and improve the overall data quality. Feedback in portals exists mostly through simple contact forms, which fail to foster meaningful collaboration or ongoing discussion. Although the French data portal, which is not based on CKAN, does provide a basic discussion functionality.

In this study, we emphasize the significance of circularity and feedback loops as a key component of collective intelligence. We propose to build a CKAN extension implementing a more advanced feedback mechanism: Issue Management, inspired by platforms like GitHub. The subsequent sections outline the schema and interface changes needed to incorporate these mechanisms into the CKAN ecosystem,

Schema Changes To implement the feedback system with issue tracking, we introduce three new tables to complement the existing *package* and *resource* tables in the CKAN database schema. The proposed tables: *issues*, *issue_comments* and *issue_log* are designed to support issue reporting, discussions, and status tracking. Figure 13 shows the schema changes required to implement issues in the database.

The *issues* table contains information about each issue — title, body, category, label, priority, status, author, created, and last modified —, linking it also to a given package id and, optionally, to a resource id (in the case, the issue is associated with a particular resource).

The *issue_comments* table links comments to a given issue and includes details about each comment in the form of text or an uploaded file, who the author was, and when it was created and last modified.

Finally, the *issue_log* table shows the change in status of each given issue over time, with the change mentioned in the action field.

Fig. 13. Schema changes required to implement feedback system through creating issues

UI/UX Changes The current user interface of CKAN does not reflect any mechanism to allow users to provide feedback in the system apart from some extensions providing a contact form. As discussed, to address that, we propose an issue management mechanism inspired by GitHub. Figure 14 shows our proposed UI changes that would add an issue/ticketing system for feedback. The dataset view is changed to add a new tab called issues. This tab lists all the issues, opened and closed, associated with the dataset. It also reflects the labels associated with each issue. Moreover, it also allows you to filter and search through the issues. The New Issue button above the grid allows the user to open up a new issue.

Fig. 14. Interface reflecting issues associated to a dataset and a mechanism to create new issue

Once a user clicks on the button to add a new issue, a new page appears (see Figure 15). This page allows the user to enter the details of the new issues. The form prompts users to provide the following details about the issue: title,

description, category, priority, and a linked resource. The linked resource refers to an existing resource within the dataset. It allows the user to associate a particular resource with the issue, or they can also leave it blank, in which case it is considered a general issue. Moreover, if the user is not signed in, the form requests the author to enter their username to enable identification and facilitate responses and comments on the issue. Apart from adding the issue, you can view the whole discussion around the issue by clicking on it from the first interface.

Figure 16 shows the proposed interface for viewing the details of an issue. It shows the details of the particular issue and all the comments associated with it in a conversation-like structure. Also, it allows you to add your own feedback regarding the issue by adding the comment. Issues that are closed no longer allow comments to avoid redundancy.

Fig. 15. Interface to open an issue for any dataset

Fig. 16. Interface to view details and comments associated to an issue of a dataset

4.4 Integration and Deployment

To integrate these features, we propose to develop them as modular extensions. It would ensure compatibility with all the CKAN-based open data portals right away. The administrators of open data portals would just have to install the extension, and the discussed changes would be integrated into their portals. Moreover, it would empower the administrators of open data portals to configure them and enable or disable them according to their specific needs.

Additionally, the extension will be added to CKAN's list of available plugins, simplifying discovery and adoption for other portal administrators. To support broader implementation, we plan to create detailed documentation, training resources, and demonstration videos of installing the extensions to encourage adoption by the community.

5 Preliminary Evaluation

5.1 Evaluation Strategy

To evaluate the efficacy of the proposed extensions, we plan to initially deploy them on select CKAN-based open data portals. In the evaluation process, we will focus on monitoring key engagement metrics such as the number of reported issues, categories of issues, user comments on them, submitted revisions, number of revisions accepted, and interactions between users and data publishers. Our goal would be to measure improvements in user participation and collaborations within the ecosystem before and after the extensions are implemented.

We will also gather qualitative feedback from publishers, users, and portal administrators to gauge how these extensions have affected their workflows. This would include gauging ease of use, relevance of the submitted feedback, number of meaningful revisions accepted by publishers, time taken to resolve issues, and time taken for a publisher to accept the revision. Moreover, we will focus on analyzing the improvement in dataset quality and reusability. Based on these evaluations, we will finetune the extensions and eventually expand their integration to all the portals.

6 Discussion and Future Work

The proposed extensions will transform CKAN-based portals into more interactive and user-driven platforms, fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. By enabling dataset revisioning and structured feedback mechanisms, these features address key challenges in data quality and usability.

In future iterations, we plan to implement these extensions more broadly and deploy them in the CKAN extension store. Moreover, inspired by OSM initiatives like the HOT Tasking Manager, we also plan to propose a hierarchical structure reflecting user expertise with 3 levels: beginner, intermediate, and expert [19]. These levels would mostly be decided by the number of revisions they have made and how active they have been in the community. We would also show a commit chart to the user to see their progress through the years. The main reason for introducing user expertise levels is to identify users who, apart from publishers, could also decide to accept or reject the revisions to speed up the process. Most publishers are associated with a large number of datasets and might not be able to address revisions in time. Additionally, it may be useful to identify the more advanced and active members of the community, in case there is a need to organize events for collaborative data processing and assign responsibilities accordingly.

We also plan to incorporate machine learning and generative AI to analyze user revisions and feedback to identify patterns in them. It would allow administrators to gauge and address the most frequent issues preemptively. Additionally, analytical visualizations of feedback and revision history for resources would be extremely helpful in this regard. Finally, we aim to conduct extensive field trials with select open data portals and gather feedback from the CKAN community

to refine the extensions further. Collaborative workshops and hackathons will be organized to promote these features and gather ideas for future enhancements.

Limitations. Despite the promise of the proposed extensions, several limitations remain. First, the adoption of such features depends on the willingness of open data portal owners and maintainers to install and configure new extensions, which may pose organizational or technical challenges. Furthermore, the effectiveness of userdriven revisioning and feedback mechanisms can vary depending on the size and engagement of the user community; in portals with low activity, these features may see limited use. Lastly, the absence of realworld deployment and formal user studies at this stage means that the practical impact of these extensions remains to be validated, which we plan to address through future pilot deployments.

7 Conclusion

This study proposes implementing dataset revisioning and feedback mechanisms to enhance collaboration and user engagement in open data portals based on CKAN. Currently, the system is publisher-driven, which provides limited opportunities for users to contribute. This lack of user involvement affects data quality and usability poorly. Structured revisioning allows users to modify and improve datasets, while the issue management system provides a platform for users to report errors, request improvements, and suggest new features. Based on previous research on other platforms that implemented these features (Github, Wikidata, OpenStreetMap), we expect that these features foster collective intelligence, enabling both technical and non-technical users to participate in enhancing data resources. The modular design of these extensions ensures easy integration into existing CKAN portals and scalability across diverse implementations. Additionally, the proposed enhancements align with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles by promoting collaboration and continuous improvement of open data through user engagement and making the ecosystem circular. These features enable CKAN portals to become more dynamic and user-driven, encouraging innovation, transparency, and long-term sustainability in open data management, resulting in a more circular ecosystem.

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